

Migration Landscape of Russia: Typology of Municipalities and Patterns of Spatial Population Mobility

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Abstract

The article examines patterns of population migration in Russia at the municipal level. Data on migration mobility and growth, by type of movement, and on the composition of migrants by sex and age for 2015–2022 were collected for 2,330 municipalities. Using digital traces from social media, the most popular travel routes from each district and region were analyzed. Migration attraction zones of Moscow, St. Petersburg, and regional centers were identified. Maps of municipal migration indicators covering the entire territory of the country were constructed. Particular attention is paid to migration in Russia's priority geostrategic territories: exclaves, the North Caucasus, the Far East, the Arctic zone, and border areas. It was found that these territories differ from the national average in most indicators of migration movement. A typology of Russian municipal entities (districts and areas) based on the size and nature of migration is proposed. Correlation analysis of municipal data showed that migration mobility has a moderate relationship with the distance to regional centers and the size of wages, while migration growth has a moderate relationship with population size, the scale of the local economy, and proximity to the administrative center. The results obtained can be used in further studies of Russia's spatial and demographic development at the subregional level.

Keywords

migration, spatial analysis, migration factors, typology, digital traces, municipalities, Russia

JEL codes: O15, J61

Introduction

As demographic tools advance, studies examining population dynamics on a large scale and with a high degree of detail are becoming increasingly common. In Russia, at the national and municipal levels, patterns of mortality (Timonin et al. 2020), fertility (Petrosyan 2021), age composition of the population (Petrosyan et al. 2019), urbanization and territorial peripherality (Karachurina and Mkrtchyan 2019), and the consequences of the pandemic (Nikitin et al. 2023) have been studied. Our article focuses on spatial patterns of population migration at the municipal level. We analyzed the intensity of migration processes, directions of movement, and the composition of migrants by gender and age. Maps of migration indicators were constructed, covering 2,330 municipalities across Russia.

The study combines data from multiple sources: official municipal statistics for 2015–2022 and digital traces – migration data extracted from user profiles on the social network VKontakte (VK.com) for 2015 and 2022. Social media provide more detailed information on population movement patterns, complementing traditional statistics. The collected data allow us to analyze migration factors at the municipal level. Previous studies primarily examined migration between constituent entities of the Russian Federation (Vakulenko 2019) or were limited to individual regions (Smirnov and Lytkina 2022).

The article begins with a review of studies on spatial patterns of migration at the subregional level, followed by a discussion of the research methodology. The results are presented in three parts: 1) patterns of migration mobility and growth 2) movement trajectories, and 3) economic and spatial factors of migration processes. The Conclusion summarizes the findings and outlines prospects for further research.

Study of population migration at the subregional level

Modern migration studies with a high degree of spatial detail can cover the entire globe. For example, an analysis of subregional migration in 216 countries (Niva et al. 2023) showed that global migration patterns are more strongly associated with the level of human development of territories than with climate. In large countries such as Russia, the USA, China, Brazil, and India, the use of detailed migration data is particularly important. Another example of a simultaneously large-scale and detailed examination of migration is a database on the share of migrants in municipalities across 22 OECD countries (Astruc-Le Souder et al. 2024). Population migration at the subregional level has been studied in many countries, including the USA (Ambinakudige and Parisi 2015), Germany (Starikova 2018), UK (Rees and Lomax 2019), Spain (González-Leonardo et al. 2022), China (Zhou et al. 2024), and the Nordic countries (Heleniak and Jokinen 2022).

In studies of population migration in Russia, several categories of subregional data sources can be distinguished. Primarily, these are official statistics, including data at the municipal and settlement levels, as well as unpublished microdata. They have been used to study movements within the settlement hierarchy (Mkrtchyan 2024), the exchange between migration centers and subcenters (Karachurina and Mkrtchyan 2021), migration distances (Karachurina and Mkrtchyan 2023), and the sex ratio of the migrating population (Gerasimov 2022). At the municipal level, analyses have focused on individual regions (Mkrtchyan and Gerasimov 2023) as well as groups of regions (Kalabikhina and Mokrensky 2017; Kashnitsky 2020; Nefedova et al. 2022; Karachurina et al. 2022).

Sociological methods, such as population surveys, can also be applied to samples of dozens of settlements (Balaban et al. 2024), but conducting surveys across all categories of settlements and regions in the country would entail enormous financial costs. Population censuses provide municipal-level data on the duration of residence of the population at their place of permanent residence, as well as on international migration.

The accumulation of large volumes of online migration data has given rise to research based on digital traces. In Russia, data from user profiles on the social media VKontakte are most commonly used. Using these data, the largest migration flows outside the capitals have been studied (Zamyatina and Yashunsky 2018); educational migrations from municipalities in Siberia have been analyzed (Chernyshev et al. 2023a; Chernyshev et al. 2023b); areas of attraction of higher education centers have been identified (Chernyshev et al. 2023); and migration trajectories in the Arctic zone (Fauzer and Smirnov 2020; Smirnov 2022b) and across Russia (Smirnov 2022a) have been mapped.

Even more precise information, both spatially and temporally, is collected by mobile operators (Mahrova et al. 2022), but access to such data is challenging for researchers. Typically, studies cover only a single region and rely on data from one operator. The use of satellite imagery also enables the study of specific types of mobility, such as seasonal or dacha-related movements (Averkiewa et al. 2016).

Despite the large number of studies using subregional data, no research covers the entire territory of Russia while providing a typology of municipalities based on key migration indicators: mobility, growth, the ratio between different types of movements, the composition of migrants by sex and age, and gravitation toward migration centers. Similarly, there are no studies analyzing spatial factors of migration across all municipalities of the country.

Methods and data

The object of this study was the first-level municipal entities (MEs) of Russia, including urban districts, municipal districts, and municipal areas. Federal cities were considered in their entirety due to the fragmentary nature of their subregional data. The primary source of information on migration and population size was the Database of Municipal Entity Indicators of Rosstat (DBMEI)¹. Data were downloaded and disaggregated by municipalities, 5-year age groups, sex, and migration direction. In total, 5.1 million records for 2015–2022 were collected, of which 15.1% were missing, primarily due to the absence of international migration in small municipalities.

During the study period, administrative-territorial changes occurred in Russia: some municipalities merged, while others were divided. For example, the Sirius urban district was separated from the Sochi urban district in 2020. Such municipalities were grouped and treated consistently throughout the study period. The total number of municipalities and cities of federal significance included in the study is 2,330, of which 28 closed administrative-territorial entities lack Rosstat migration data.

Many missing values were identified in the DBMEI. Three techniques were employed to improve data quality. First, because cities of federal significance are subjects of the Russian Federation, data for these cities were supplemented from the Unified Interdepartmen-

¹ DBMEI (Database of Municipal Entity Indicators). Rosstat. <https://rosstat.gov.ru/storage/mediabank/munstm.htm>

tal Information and Statistical System (UIISS)². Second, if data were missing for municipal areas but available for individual urban and rural settlements within those districts, missing values were imputed by summing the settlement-level data. If data were missing for one type of migration but available for others and for total migration, the missing values were estimated by subtraction. Third, given that the study period spans eight years and only average values were used, missing individual data points had a limited impact on the final indicators.

Municipal statistics were supplemented with “digital traces” of the population obtained from user profiles on the social media VK.com. Two datasets on migration flows by municipality were used. The first was collected in 2015 as part of the Virtual Population of Russia project, supported by the Russian Geographical Society, and contains 3.8 million records of migration movements. The second dataset was compiled in 2022 as part of a Russian Science Foundation project (Chernyshev et al. 2023) and includes information on 1.6 million movements. While the first dataset covers general migration (changes of residence and educational moves), the second focuses exclusively on educational migration – from the place of birth or schooling to the location of the university.

The value of digital traces lies in their ability to provide information on specific directions of movement. These “checkerboard patterns” from departure territories to destination territories are not available in official statistics. In this study, outgoing migration flows from each territory were analyzed, allowing the identification of the largest migration directions as well as the number of total and educational movements to Moscow and St. Petersburg.

Data processing algorithms were implemented in the Julia programming language using the DataFrames.jl and CSV.jl packages, and maps were constructed with the VegaLite.jl package. The collected data for all municipalities are publicly available (Migration flows and networks).

To better explain migration patterns, the article uses municipal groupings. According to administrative status, five groups of municipal entities are distinguished: 3 cities of federal significance, 80 urban districts that are regional capitals, 501 other urban districts, 400 municipal districts, and 1,346 municipal areas. The typology of municipalities corresponds to the administrative-territorial division and municipal structure of Russia as of early 2024.

Based on population size, nine groups of municipalities are distinguished. The group with the largest population (over 2 million people) includes only Moscow and St. Petersburg, while the smallest group (less than 10,000) comprises 357 municipalities. The largest group, with populations between 10,000 and 25,000, includes 907 municipalities.

Territories are also grouped according to spatial criteria. Four groups of priority geostrategic territories are identified in the *Strategy for Spatial Development of the Russian Federation* (Order of the Government of the Russian Federation 2019):

1. Regions with an exclave position: Kaliningrad Oblast, the Republic of Crimea, and Sevastopol (48 MEs in total);
2. North Caucasian Federal District (143 MEs);
3. Far Eastern Federal District within its post-2018 borders (230 MEs);
4. Territories of the Arctic zone of the Russian Federation (77 MEs across nine regions) (Federal Law 2020).

In addition to the Arctic zone, a broader category of territories of the Far North and equivalent localities is considered, including 294 municipal entities to which northern benefits and social guarantees apply (RF Government Resolution 2021).

2 UIISS (Unified Interdepartmental Information and Statistical System). <https://fedstat.ru>

The spatial development strategy also designates border regions as geostrategic territories. Using municipal data, only municipalities directly adjacent to the land state border – from Norway to the DPRK – were identified. Together with the border territories of Kaliningrad Oblast, their total number amounts to 232. Russia's geostrategic territories are of particular interest from economic, cultural, and security perspectives.

Territorial patterns of migration in Russia

According to Rosstat, the migration mobility (gross migration rate) – defined as the sum of migrants and out-migrants per 1,000 inhabitants – varies by an order of magnitude between territories. In the gold-mining municipality of Egvekinot in Chukotka, it reaches 392.5, while in the Untsukul'sky District of Dagestan it is only 9.7 (Figure 1). The highest mobility rates are observed in remote and inaccessible areas of the Far East, as well as on Novaya Zemlya. Low values are found primarily in the North Caucasian republics, including Dagestan, Kabardino-Balkaria, the Chechen Republic, and Ingushetia. The average rate across all municipalities is 71.9.

Figure 1. Gross migration rate per 1,000 inhabitants by municipalities of Russia, 2015–2022. *Source:* compiled from Rosstat DBMEI.

Mobility is slightly below average in regional capitals and urban districts, where residents have more opportunities to realize their life strategies without relocating. In general, the smaller the population of a municipality, the higher its migration mobility. Municipalities with fewer than 10,000 inhabitants are particularly notable, with an average mobility of 90.1. Among geostrategic territories, the lowest mobility is recorded in the North Caucasus (40.5), while the highest is in the Arctic territories (114.2). Frequent staff turnover supports the viability of remote Arctic settlements, where long-term work poses health risks. In exclaves and border areas, mobility levels vary significantly depending on the region.

Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between two types of intra-Russian migration. Areas where intraregional mobility predominates are shown in green, while those where interregional mobility prevails are shown in purple. In 70.7% of municipalities, intraregional exchange exceeds interregional exchange. On average, the share of interregional exchange across all municipalities is 41.1%. This share is significantly higher in regional administrative centers (52.6%) as well as in cities with populations exceeding 100,000 residents.

Figure 2. The ratio of interregional and intraregional migration turnover in the municipalities of Russia, 2015–2022, %. *Source:* compiled from Rosstat DBMEI.

Five groups of territories can be identified where interregional exchange predominates.

First, territories located near Moscow and St. Petersburg that fall within their zones of gravitational influence.

Second, territories situated near large cities in other regions. For example, the western part of Kurgan Oblast gravitates toward Chelyabinsk, while the Jewish Autonomous Oblast is oriented toward Khabarovsk.

Third, northern mining regions with high income levels, which can be identified by the sectoral structure of employment (Romashina 2020).

Fourth, resort areas of Krasnodar Krai and Crimea, which attract residents from other regions due to favorable natural and climatic conditions.

Fifth, the North Caucasus. Low levels of intraregional migration within the Caucasian republics may be explained by relatively homogeneous economic development combined with linguistic and cultural heterogeneity, while high interregional migration can be associated with the influence of diaspora networks.

Among geostrategic territories, the highest average share of interregional exchange is recorded in the North Caucasus (56.2%) and the Arctic zone (51.5%), while the lowest is observed in the Far East (38.3%). Large distances between settlement centers in the eastern part of the country hinder migration to other regions. In 18 districts of Yakutia and Krasnoyarsk Krai, the share of interregional exchange is below 10%, and in Churapchinsky District

it is below 3%. These territories are predominantly inhabited by indigenous peoples of the North, who are less inclined toward interregional migration.

The highest shares of interregional exchange are observed in Moscow (96.5%), the North Kurilsky District (96.4%), the Nogai Municipal Area of Dagestan (95.0%), and the Arctic cities of Pevek (93.6%), Vorkuta (91.2%), and the Bilibino District (90.2%).

The average share of international migration in total migration turnover across municipalities was only 7.1% (Figure 3). Among regional capitals, this figure reaches 16.4%, and among cities with a population of over one million, 17.4%.

Figure 3. Share of international migration in total migration turnover in the municipalities of Russia, 2015–2022, %. *Source:* compiled from Rosstat DBMEI.

Among geostrategic territories, exclaves (14.2%) located near foreign states show the highest values. In border areas, the share of international migration is also slightly above the national average (7.4%). Although the difference may appear modest, border areas generally lack large cities that attract foreign migrants.

The share of international migration is higher in territories adjacent to post-Soviet states where the Russian language remains widespread (Kazakhstan, Belarus, Ukraine, Estonia). For example, the average share of international exchange in municipal areas of Altai Krai bordering Kazakhstan is 8.3%, compared to 2.9% in the rest of the region. In Astrakhan Oblast, the respective figures are 10.4% and 7.0%, and in Kurgan Oblast, 3.7% and 2.6%.

Areas bordering Mongolia and Finland differ little in terms of the share of international migration compared with other parts of their respective regions. International exchange is also low in the regions of the North Caucasus (4.0%), despite their proximity to the countries of Transcaucasia.

According to Rosstat data, international migration was completely absent in 15 municipalities during the study period, seven of which are located in the Republic of Tyva. In 18 municipalities, international migration accounts for more than one-third of total movements, and in Kaluga it accounts for just over half.

The magnitude of the net migration rate varies considerably across municipalities of different sizes and administrative statuses. The average value for all Russian municipalities is negative, amounting to -3.7 per 1,000 residents. At the same time, high positive values are observed in cities of federal significance (12.0) and in regional administrative centres (2.2). In other urban districts, growth is negligible (0.04).

Positive average growth is recorded in municipalities with populations exceeding 50,000. In cities with over one million residents, the net migration rate reaches 3.2; in cities with around 500,000 residents, 7.0; in the 250,000–500,000 group, 4.9; and in the 100,000–250,000 group, 3.5. In the smallest municipalities (fewer than 10,000 residents), the average migration loss is 8.3 per 1,000 inhabitants.

Among geostrategic territories, positive growth is observed only in exclaves (3.9). A moderate decline is recorded in the North Caucasus (-1.7). In the remaining geostrategic groups, the decline is substantially more pronounced: the Arctic zone (-5.4), border areas (-6.1), and the Far East (-7.1). These data confirm the persistence of a “western drift” and continued outmigration from the regions of the Far North.

Areas experiencing population growth are typically located near large cities (Figure 4). However, some remote territories with high positive growth also stand out, including Egvekinot Urban District in Chukotka and Novaya Zemlya. High growth rates are also observed in resort towns such as Anapa (25.9), Goryachy Klyuch (25.5), Sochi (13.2), Alushta (12.5), and Yalta (9.2).

Figure 4. Net migration rate per 1000 inhabitants by municipalities of Russia, 2015–2022. *Source:* compiled from Rosstat DBMEI.

Among the municipalities with the most pronounced relative decline are numerous northern territories in Magadan Oblast, Arkhangelsk Oblast, and the Komi Republic. Decline is also characteristic of areas along the country’s southern border in Zabaykalsky Krai and Orenburg Oblast. Among other regions, Kirov Oblast stands out: it contains 17 of the 100 municipalities with the highest rates of population decline in Russia.

Let us consider a two-dimensional typology of municipalities based on migration growth and mobility (Table 1). Municipalities with high population mobility are distributed relatively evenly across the three categories of migration increase and decrease. Among munic-

Table 1. Distribution of municipalities in Russia by migration increase/decrease and migration mobility, 2015–2022

Grouping of municipalities	Number of ME	Migration increase ($\geq 0\%$)			Moderate loss, less than 10 %			High loss, more than 10 %			No data
		Migration mobility, ‰									
		>80	60-80	<60	>80	60-80	<60	>80	60-80	<60	
All ME	2330	177	172	161	360	459	553	212	135	73	28
<i>by status:</i>											
cities of federal significance	3	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
regional centers	80	9	17	22	7	5	19	1	-	-	-
other urban districts	501	49	56	69	43	77	151	12	9	7	28
municipal districts	400	15	11	3	89	100	49	85	36	12	-
municipal areas	1346	103	87	66	221	277	334	114	90	54	-
<i>by number:</i>											
over 2 million people	2	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
from 1 to 2 million	14	-	3	7	-	-	4	-	-	-	-
from 500 thous. to 1 million	24	4	4	10	-	1	5	-	-	-	-
from 250 to 500 thousand	50	9	10	12	2	3	14	-	-	-	-
from 100 to 250 thousand	156	21	22	40	9	10	52	-	-	1	1
from 50 to 100 thousand	296	35	35	40	13	41	120	1	3	1	7
from 25 to 50 thousand	524	38	56	33	62	117	174	15	9	16	4
from 10 to 25 thousand	907	45	34	16	200	227	155	95	86	44	5
less than 10 thousand	357	25	7	2	74	60	29	101	37	11	11
<i>by location:</i>											
exclaves	48	7	4	17	5	6	8	-	1	-	-
North Caucasus	143	1	6	25	-	11	91	-	2	7	-
Far East	230	22	10	1	61	31	13	41	37	12	2
Arctic zone	77	10	-	-	27	5	3	23	4	-	5
Far North	294	33	4	-	78	42	18	73	32	7	7
border	232	19	14	9	42	40	36	33	22	17	-

Source: compiled from Rosstat DBMEI.

ipalities with average mobility, 60.0% exhibit moderate migration loss, while among those with low mobility the share reaches 70.3%. A combination of high loss and low mobility is virtually absent.

The largest cities combine migration growth with medium or low mobility. The only municipality with a population exceeding 100,000 that experiences high migration loss is Nakhodka Urban District in Primorsky Krai. Medium-sized municipalities are typically characterised by moderate decline combined with low mobility. The smallest municipalities (fewer than 10,000 residents) generally display high mobility alongside high or moderate population decline.

Among the priority geostrategic territories, the North Caucasus demonstrates the most distinct migration profile: 63.6% of its municipalities fall into the category of moderate decline and low mobility. Border areas are the most heterogeneous in terms of migration intensity. No single one of the nine types accounts for more than 18% of border municipalities.

Figure 5 and Table 2 present a typology of Russian municipalities based on the sign of the migration balance for three types of movement: intraregional, interregional, and international.

Figure 5. Types of municipalities in Russia according to the sign of the migration balance for three types of movement, 2015–2022. *Source:* compiled from Rosstat DBMEI.

Type 1 includes municipalities where positive migration balance is observed for all three types. Only 145 municipalities (6.2%) fall into this category. These include all cities of federal significance – Moscow, St Petersburg, and Sevastopol.

The majority of municipalities (1,455 or 62.4%) belong to Type 4, characterised by negative intraregional and interregional balances combined with positive international migration. Rural areas of Russia are predominantly associated with this type.

Type 3 is also relatively widespread: it is defined by a positive interregional balance combined with negative balances in the other two categories. This group includes more than half

Table 2. Distribution of municipalities in Russia by migration increase/decrease and directions of movement, 2015–2022.

Grouping of municipalities	Number of ME	Types of municipalities by growth/decrease (within a region / between regions / international)								no data
		type 1	type 2	type 3	type 4	type 5	type 6	type 7	type 8	
		+++	++	+-	--	+-	--	+-	--	
All ME	2330	145	217	267	1455	7	13	25	173	28
<i>by status:</i>										
cities of federal significance	3	3	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
regional centers	80	11	3	42	15	1	–	7	1	–
other urban districts	501	54	49	106	220	2	4	5	33	28
municipal districts	400	8	29	28	291	–	–	2	42	–
municipal areas	1346	69	136	91	929	4	9	11	97	–
<i>by number:</i>										
over 2 million people	2	2	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
from 1 to 2 million	14	5	1	6	2	–	–	–	–	–
from 500 thousand to 1 million	24	6	1	12	5	–	–	–	–	–
from 250 to 500 thousand	50	9	5	21	10	–	–	3	2	–
from 100 to 250 thousand	156	32	24	43	39	1	2	4	10	1
from 50 to 100 thousand	296	34	31	56	136	2	1	8	21	7
from 25 to 50 thousand	524	32	59	63	336	1	1	2	26	4
from 10 to 25 thousand	907	19	63	60	666	3	7	4	80	5
less than 10 thousand	357	6	33	6	261	–	2	4	34	11
<i>by location:</i>										
exclaves	48	10	22	1	15	–	–	–	–	–
North Caucasus	143	9	15	31	78	1	–	4	5	–
Far East	230	6	19	31	143	–	2	6	21	2
Arctic zone	77	2	5	14	45	–	1	–	5	5
Far North	294	6	25	41	186	1	5	4	19	7
border	232	7	15	13	166	–	2	5	24	–

Source: compiled from Rosstat DBMEI.

of the regional capitals that are less migration-attractive than Moscow and St Petersburg, as well as a substantial number of urban districts.

The rarest category, Type 5, combines a negative international balance with positive balances in the other two types of movement. This group includes only seven municipalities.

Type 8 (negative balance in all three directions) comprises 173 municipalities (7.4%), primarily small municipal districts.

Among the priority geostrategic territories, exclaves are distinctive: they most frequently belong to Type 2 (negative intraregional balance combined with positive interregional and international balances). In the remaining geostrategic groups, Type 4 predominates. Among border municipalities, 71.6% fall into this category, while a further 10.3% belong to Type 8, exhibiting negative balances across all types of movement.

Of the socio-demographic characteristics of migrants, the DBMEI provides data only on sex and age. In only 258 municipalities (11.2%) do men account for more than half of all movements (Figure 6). Migration in contemporary Russia is predominantly female, reflecting both the population composition and the higher early mortality of men.

Figure 6. Share of women in migration turnover in the municipalities of Russia, 2015-2022, %. *Source:* compiled from Rosstat DBMEI.

Male predominance in migration is observed in certain municipalities of the Far East and Arctic regions. Territories where women contribute more than 60% of migration include Shipunovsky Municipal Area in Altai Krai and nine districts in Tyva. The relatively low migration activity of men in these areas is likely linked not only to early mortality but also to general socio-economic disadvantage, poverty, and high rates of alcoholism.

Among the priority geostrategic territories, the Arctic zone exhibits the most balanced sex ratio of migrants (50.4% women). Even in the Arctic, where employment in extractive industries and transport is high, women still predominate. Conversely, the least balanced

geostrategic territory is the North Caucasus, where women account for an average of 52.6% of all migration movements.

The average age of migrants in the vast majority of municipalities ranges between 27 and 35 years (Figure 7). The young age of migrants in some national republics suggests that migration there is primarily associated with education or labour mobility of young people. Higher average ages are observed mainly in the western regions of the country, such as Pskov Oblast, where the proportion of elderly residents in the population is relatively high.

Figure 7. Average age and proportion of elderly migrants in the municipalities of Russia, 2015–2022, %. *Source:* compiled from Rosstat DBMEI.

Certain territories are also identified where resettlement programmes for residents from the Far North are being implemented, including Vorkuta, Ina, and Magadan Oblast. The map showing the proportion of elderly migrants closely mirrors the map of the share of people beyond working age in the population (Petrosyan et al. 2019: 72).

Among the priority geostrategic territories, the lowest average proportion of elderly migrants is observed in the North Caucasus (4.0%), while the highest is in exclaves (6.6%). When interpreting these results, it should be noted that age-specific migration rates can be particularly distorted by “automatic returns,” i.e., departures automatically recorded after the completion of temporary registration. Data derived from digital sources do not have this limitation.

Migration trajectories in Russia

According to digital traces from VK.com user profiles for 2015, residents of 1,799 municipalities (77.4% of the total) most frequently choose their regional capital as their travel destination (Table 3, Figure 8). Among the remaining municipalities, the most common destinations are Moscow (200 municipalities), St Petersburg (71), and a non-capital city within their own region (155).

Among non-capital cities, the most frequently selected destinations are Biysk (8 municipalities), Novokuznetsk (7), Cherepovets (6), Orsk and Pyatigorsk (5 each), Sterlitamak, Magnitogorsk, Neftekamsk (4 each), and Buzuluk, Velikiye Luki, Glazov, Naberezhnye Chelny, Nazran, and Ukhta (3 each).

Residents of 94 municipalities most often move to the capital of another region: Tyumen (22 municipalities, mainly from Khanty-Mansiysk and Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrugs), Yekaterinburg, Krasnoyarsk, Novosibirsk (7 each), Krasnodar (6), Samara, Khabarovsk, Chelyabinsk (4 each), and Stavropol (3). Only six municipalities have a predominant migration flow to other regions outside the regional capitals.

Among regional centres, 76.3% of migration flows gravitate towards Moscow, and 8.8% towards St Petersburg. Residents of urban districts are more likely to move to Moscow than those of municipal districts or municipal areas. In municipalities with populations exceeding 250,000, flows to the federal capital surpass flows to the regional capital.

Among the priority geostrategic territories, the Arctic zone stands out: 20.8% of municipalities in this zone gravitate towards St Petersburg, a proportion significantly higher than the national average of 3.0%. These are mainly urban districts in the European Arctic.

Considering only educational migration, based on a later VK.com dataset for 2022, the main patterns remain similar (Table 4). In 2,004 out of 2,302 municipalities (87.1%), the predominant migration direction is consistent across both datasets. The share of regional capitals and St Petersburg has increased slightly, while Moscow’s share has decreased.

Among exclave territories, 93.8% of municipalities gravitate towards their regional capitals, and among border territories, 88.6%, which is higher than in the previous dataset. The share of Arctic municipalities within the St Petersburg gravity zone has increased further to 27.6%. Territories in regions without universities – namely the Nenets, Yamalo-Nenets, and Chukotka Autonomous Okrugs – naturally do not gravitate towards their regional capitals in terms of educational migration.

Let us examine outgoing flows to Moscow and St Petersburg in greater detail (Figure 9). The average share of Moscow among movements to the two capitals across all municipalities was 67.9% in 2015. The population size of a municipality has little influence on residents’

Table 3. Distribution of municipalities in Russia by the predominant direction of migration, 2015

Grouping of municipalities	Number of ME	Predominant direction of movement						No data
		Moscow	St. Petersburg	Capital of its region	Capital of another region	Not the capital of its region	Not the capital in another region	
All ME	2330	200	71	1799	94	155	6	5
<i>by status:</i>								
cities of federal significance	3	2	1	–	–	–	–	–
regional centers	80	61	7	–	10	1	1	–
other urban districts	501	98	16	334	32	19	1	1
municipal districts	400	6	14	334	16	30	–	–
municipal areas	1346	33	33	1131	36	105	4	4
<i>by number:</i>								
over 2 million people	2	1	1	–	–	–	–	–
from 1 to 2 million	14	14	–	–	–	–	–	–
from 500 thousand to 1 million	24	19	1	2	1	–	1	–
from 250 to 500 thousand	50	37	5	7	1	–	–	–
from 100 to 250 thousand	156	41	9	88	10	8	–	–
from 50 to 100 thousand	296	37	15	211	17	15	1	–
from 25 to 50 thousand	524	25	13	415	21	48	2	–
from 10 to 25 thousand	907	15	19	765	35	70	1	2
less than 10 thousand	357	11	8	311	9	14	1	3
<i>by location:</i>								
exclaves	48	4	–	40	–	4	–	–
North Caucasus	143	23	–	98	5	13	1	3
Far East	230	12	1	200	11	6	–	–
Arctic zone	77	7	16	43	11	–	–	–
Far North	294	13	26	208	32	14	–	1
border	232	9	10	191	6	14	–	2

Source: compiled based on data from the “Virtual Population of Russia” project.

preferences. The only exceptions are the smallest municipalities, where Moscow’s share is lower, at 61.5%.

Territorial patterns are more pronounced. In the North Caucasus, Moscow accounts for 75.0% of flows to the two capitals, while the Arctic is the only group of priority geostrategic territories gravitating towards St Petersburg (Moscow’s share is 44.7%). Territories in the Northwestern Federal District, as well as some Asian territories, are predominantly drawn to the northern capital, particularly when considering educational migration.

Figure 8. Predominant direction of movement by municipalities in Russia, according to VK.com profile data for 2015 and 2022. *Source:* compiled from datasets of the “Virtual Population of Russia” and “Inter-Municipal Educational Migration in Russia” projects.

Table 4. Distribution of municipalities in Russia by the predominant destination for educational migration, 2022.

Grouping of municipalities	Number of ME	Predominant direction of movement (education)						
		Moscow	St. Petersburg	Capital of its region	Capital of another region	Not the capital of its region	Not the capital in another region	No data
All ME	2330	152	79	1880	131	57	2	29
<i>by status:</i>								
cities of federal significance	3	1	1	–	1	–	–	–
regional centers	80	51	12	–	15	1	1	–
other urban districts	501	72	18	340	42	11	1	17
municipal districts	400	3	14	357	18	8	–	–
municipal areas	1346	25	34	1183	55	37	–	12
<i>by number:</i>								
over 2 million people	2	1	1	–	–	–	–	–
from 1 to 2 million	14	12	1	–	–	1	–	–
from 500 thousand to 1 million	24	17	1	2	4	–	–	–
from 250 to 500 thousand	50	31	6	7	5	–	1	–
from 100 to 250 thousand	156	30	9	100	11	5	–	1
from 50 to 100 thousand	296	24	15	223	21	9	1	3
from 25 to 50 thousand	524	14	16	441	31	18	–	4
from 10 to 25 thousand	907	13	20	800	48	19	–	7
less than 10 thousand	357	10	10	307	11	5	–	14
<i>by location:</i>								
exclaves	48	–	1	45	1	–	1	–
North Caucasus	143	15	–	111	6	9	–	2
Far East	230	8	6	186	21	1	–	8
Arctic zone	77	4	21	34	17	–	–	1
Far North	294	5	35	189	52	6	–	7
border	232	4	10	205	8	4	–	1

Source: compiled from the dataset “Inter-municipal educational migration in Russia”.

Figure 9. Ratio of movements to Moscow and St Petersburg in the municipalities of Russia, based on VK.com profile data for 2015 and 2022. *Source:* compiled from datasets of the “Virtual Population of Russia” and “Inter-Municipal Educational Migration in Russia” projects.

According to the 2022 dataset, Moscow’s average share is slightly lower at 65.6%, while in the Arctic it falls to 37.6%. Fewer than half of residents in the municipalities of the Far North (47.2%) and exclaves (49.9%) choose Moscow over the two capital cities for educational purposes.

Municipal data, combined with mapping methods, demonstrate a high degree of spatial unevenness across all migration indicators. These analyses confirm that Russia’s priority geo-strategic territories frequently exhibit atypical migration patterns.

Factors of population migration at the municipal level

The extensive array of subregional data collected allows us to pose the question: what factors influence the observed mosaic pattern of population migration? To address this question, several additional indicators available at the municipal level were introduced, and a correlation analysis was performed.

It is well established that population movements generally occur upwards along the settlement hierarchy, and that upward flows tend to be more effective (Mkrtchyan and Gilmanov 2023). Capital cities are often the largest in terms of population; accordingly, the first indicator considered is the population size of the municipality.

Another important factor is the range of travel. It has been reported that 31.3% of internal Russian relocations occur over very short distances, not exceeding 50 km, and 43.5% over distances up to 100 km (Karachurina and Mkrtchyan 2023). Based on this, the distance from a municipality to its regional centre, measured in a straight line, was selected as the second indicator. As previously established, regional centres are the most common travel destinations for most municipalities.

Two additional indicators reflect the economic situation within the municipality and were obtained from the DBMEI: “Average monthly wages of employees of organisations” and “Shipped goods of own production, performed works and services using own means.” For brevity, the latter will be referred to as the scale of the local economy. A limitation of both indicators is that they do not capture the contribution of small businesses. To minimise the impact of inflation and gaps in the database, the values of both indicators were divided by the median values for all municipalities in Russia for the corresponding years, and the average values were then calculated for the period 2015–2022. These normalised indicators indicate how many times wages or the volume of the local economy in a municipality are higher or lower than the median level across all territories in the country.

The spatial distribution of indicators is highly uneven (Figure 10). For example, even in northern regions without large-scale mining industries, wage indicators exceed the median level due to northern and regional coefficients (allowances). While Moscow clearly leads in terms of economic scale – exceeding the median by a factor of 6,500 – it ranks only eighth in terms of wage levels (368% of the median), whereas Nogliki Urban District on Sakhalin tops the wage rankings at 444%. The lowest wages (61.8% of the median) are observed in Gornomariysky Area of the Mari El Republic. It should be noted that low wages and economic scale in some areas, particularly those suitable for agriculture, may be partially offset by small businesses and the informal economy, which are not captured by municipal statistics.

Indicators with values spanning several orders of magnitude were logarithmically transformed. These include population size, distances in kilometres, and the scale of the local economy. The resulting correlation matrix (Table 5) indicates the absence of strong relationships, which is unsurprising given the large number of observations and the complexity of migration as a social phenomenon. Nevertheless, several moderate relationships between variables were identified.

Migration mobility exhibits the strongest linear relationship (0.36) with wage levels. Higher incomes accelerate migration flows but do not necessarily result in population growth. Another indicator correlated with the gross migration rate is population size (−0.34). Residents of larger municipalities move less frequently, owing to greater infrastructure saturation and the diversification of local labour markets.

The net migration rate correlates with three indicators: distance to the regional administrative centre (-0.42), population size (0.38), and the scale of the local economy (0.31). Centrality and economic scale make a municipality more attractive. While higher wages tend to encourage temporary migration, a substantial local economy stimulates growth of the permanent population. The economic scale indicator exerts the strongest influence on the share of international migration in total flows (0.42). A larger local economy generates employment opportunities and a multicultural environment, enhancing the attractiveness of these areas to foreign migrants.

Figure 10. Ratio of wages and the scale of the local economy (excluding small and medium-sized enterprises) in the municipalities of Russia relative to the median level, 2015–2022. *Source:* compiled from Rosstat DBMEI.

Table 5. Correlation matrix of municipal indicators in Russia, 2015–2022 (n = 2,302)

	Log(population)	Log(distance to center)	Salary (excluding small business)	Log(scale of the economy)	Gross migration rate	Net migration rate	Share of international migration	Proportion of women	Virtual net migration rate	Share of departures to Moscow and St. Petersburg
Log(population)	1									
Log(distance to admin. center)	-0.48	1								
Salary (excluding small business)	0.12	0.18	1							
Log(scale of the economy)	0.72	-0.26	0.52	1						
Gross migration rate	-0.34	0.21	0.36	-0.09	1					
Net migration rate	0.38	-0.42	0.10	0.31	0.14	1				
Share of international migration.	0.38	-0.35	0.18	0.42	0.03	0.35	1			
The proportion of women among migrants	-0.04	0.05	-0.32	-0.17	-0.26	-0.15	-0.44	1		
Virtual net migration rate	0.37	-0.13	0.01	0.30	-0.16	0.13	0.14	0.06	1	
Share of departures to Moscow and St. Petersburg	0.39	-0.24	0.21	0.32	-0.05	0.27	0.32	-0.14	0.38	1

Source: author’s calculations based on data from the DBMEI and the “Virtual Population of Russia” project.

The sex ratio among migrants is most strongly correlated with wage levels (-0.32). This suggests that higher salaries may incentivise men to migrate, whereas the proportion of educational migration is greater among women.

Virtual net migration rate is an analogue of the net migration rate for the virtual population, calculated using digital trace data. The population size was taken as the total number of users from the corresponding territory. This indicator correlates with population size (0.37) and economic scale (0.30). The final indicator in the table reflects the share of movements to Moscow and St Petersburg in the total number of departures. This indicator also exhibits the highest correlation coefficients with population size (0.39) and economic scale (0.32). Larger municipalities tend to have fewer departures to non-capital cities.

Thus, economic development exerts an influence on migration comparable to that of spatial and demographic factors. For a more comprehensive understanding of migration processes, additional determinants should be considered. These include, in particular, the infrastructure of higher and secondary vocational education, given that a substantial proportion of migration is education-related. The national composition should also be taken into account, as indigenous and small ethnic groups may exhibit atypical migratory behaviour.

The use of indicators reflecting the development of entrepreneurship, natural, climatic, and environmental conditions, and the quality of life of the population may prove informative. The explanatory power of migration models could be enhanced by considering indicators separately for different age and sex groups, as they demonstrate varying propensities for specific types of migration. For instance, in the Arctic zone of Russia, the intensity of out-migration among the elderly is primarily determined by municipal income levels and distance to the regional centre, whereas for younger populations it is influenced by ethnic composition and the availability of educational infrastructure (Smirnov 2025).

Conclusion

Data on migration at the municipal level enabled the classification of all municipalities in Russia according to indicators of spatial population mobility. Patterns in migration mobility, net migration, and the composition of migrants by sex and age were identified. Social media data enriched the study by providing additional information on population movement patterns and allowed for the identification of capital city magnet zones. By averaging data over an eight-year period and employing cartographic methods, the study covered the entire territory of Russia while maintaining a high degree of detail, thereby illustrating the country's migration landscape.

The analysis demonstrates that territories designated as priorities in the Strategy for Spatial Development of Russia exhibit distinct migration characteristics. Particularly notable are the Arctic zone – the most mobile macroregion of the country – and the North Caucasus, which is the least mobile. Exclave and border territories are characterised by high levels of international mobility. The largest macroregions, such as the Far East and the Far North, display heterogeneity in migration indicators.

Correlation analysis revealed that indicators such as population size, distance between municipalities, salary, and the scale of the local economy are associated with spatial mobility. Salary and population size better explain variation in mobility, whereas distance to the administrative centre and the volume of goods and services produced describe population growth or decline. Supplementing the collected data with additional characteristics of municipalities, including infrastructure, population composition, and quality of life, would allow the construction of more accurate models to explain local migration dynamics. The results obtained can be applied in demographic forecasting and in further studies of Russia's spatial development at the subregional level.

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